

Fractal analysis of AIDS prevalence across economic demographics

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ABSTRACT

The percentage of reported Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome infections differ from one country to another. Thus, this paper illustrates the prevalence of AIDS among different countries across the globe. The data shows that the number of people who gets infected with AIDS does not follow a normal distribution. The analysis of this AIDS prevalence has been observed to follow a fluctuating pattern and so the researchers attempt to present a fractal model of the said phenomenon. Results reveal a seemingly considerable fractal dimension of prevalence. It further exposes that countries with high percentage of reported AIDS cases follow a more fractal distribution than those in countries with lower percents reported. Furthermore, majority of the countries have AIDS prevalences which are concentrated near or on the mean fractal dimension value.

Keywords: *AIDS, prevalence, fractal dimension, fractal model*

I. INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, humans have been plagued by various diseases. Malaria, cholera, TB, flu, small pox, AIDS and many more are caused by organisms which easily reproduce and evolve. Rapid multiplication and easy transport of these disease-causing microbes are facilitated as human populations start to domesticate animals, store food, construct dams and wells, exponentially grow in number and become more mobile. Of all these diseases, the prevalence of AIDS epidemic has become a serious concern for humans. Technological and medical advancements helped eradicate this disease.

Study of the initial stages of HIV transmission along a socio-geographic network -- a large, complex, spatially focused social network with possibly fractal geometry -- is extended to include

interaction between a low-dimensional ghettoized 'core group' within which the disease spreads very rapidly and a higher dimensional, more loosely structured 'general population' in which spread is relatively slow. A mathematical modeling exercise suggests that contextually modulated interaction between them can be highly nonlinear and may greatly increase the initial rate of disease transmission within the general population (Wallace, 1992).

For decades now, people continue to suffer from AIDS. In 2011, 34.2 million people were infected and 1.7 million died (UNAID, 2011). A number of factors may be attributed to the rapid transmission of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) that causes the disease. These factors

include, among others, lifestyle, cultural practices, poverty, lack of education, poor social services, and even climate change. "Populations with currently high rates of HIV are the most vulnerable to a worsening or prolongation of the epidemic due to climate change" (Butler, 2009).

The factors for the easy transmission are as fractal as its prevalence in various countries. In fact, the HIV itself is very fractal. Medical solutions in understanding the fractality of the virus include the use of nano-scale drug (Huan- He, 2008) and the use of a vaccine which aims at training the human mind to recognize the patterns of the AIDS virus (Mukul Pal, 2008).

Viruses have very high fractal dimensions than the infected cells. Since they have higher fractal dimension, they have higher metabolic rates than the infected cells and can have enough energy to reproduce. This is very fatal to the invaded cells. However, recent developments in fractal analysis shed light to the possible solution to the AIDS problem. One breakthrough is by nanotechnology wherein a nano-scale drug will smoothen the surfaces body of the virus and consequently lessen its metabolic rate (Huan-He, 2008).

This makes understanding the nature of AIDS occurrence so puzzling in the minds of people. Thus, in order to comprehend on this phenomenon, this study attempts to find out the fractal dimensions of AIDS prevalence in developed, developing and under developed countries. In trying to develop a method to analyze the prevalence of an HIV-caused acquired immune deficiency syndrome, the researchers present a model that also conform to the fractal nature of viruses. AIDS has been reported globally, at different scales, in different periods. Reporting AIDS cases has become one of the most essential ingredients to the development of solutions for the decline of the plague. In this paper, a paradigm of HIV (human immunodeficiency virus) transmission along very large sociogeographic networks is extended to include fractal structures.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Despite the chaotic situation brought about by the AIDS epidemic in many nations, there is a fractality or pattern observed in this phenomenon. Illumination on the fractality of the AIDS phenomenon and the AIDS virus itself may eventually help solve the problem. UN Secretary General Ban says "the UN goal of halting and reversing the spread of AIDS will be met by 2015". Furthermore, he says "that more than half of the low and middle income countries are receiving

HIV and AIDS around the world

The overwhelming majority of people with HIV live in low- and middle-income countries. Sub-Saharan Africa accounts for two-thirds of all infected people. South and South-East Asia have the second highest number of people living with HIV.

treatments. However, the antiretroviral therapy must be expanded.” Concerted effort by the philanthropists, human rights advocates, health workers, scientists and mathematicians lead closer to this goal. Fractality is one dimension which may help the human race understand the epidemiology of HIV. AIDS affects the political, social and economic situation of any government. The study focuses on the prevalence of AIDS across economic tier. This has a cyclical effect to the economy – like a trap. Poor economy speeds up transmission and prevalence of AIDS in a country. Impoverished families receive poor health care and resort to migration or prostitution. Likewise, the economy of a country is affected by high prevalence of AIDS. Poor economy consequently causes high AIDS prevalence. The HIV/AIDS epidemic affects the economy in fractal ways: (a) by reversing or slowing the growth in labor supply; (b) by decreasing the savings and investments of families; and (c) by diverting the expenditures to health spending.

III. RESULTS

HISTOGRAM OF COMPUTED LAMBDA (AIDS PREVALENCE)

TIME SERIES PLOT OF COMPUTED LAMBDA (AIDS PREVALENCE)

Descriptive Statistics:

Variable	N	N*	Mean	Median	TrMean	StDev
AIDSlambda	140	1	1.2001	1.1693	1.1916	0.1278

Variable	SE Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Q1	Q3
AIDSlambda	0.0108	1.0488	1.6379	1.1016	1.2863

Based on data, the mean lambda which is 1.2 indicates that the data are ruggedly distributed. Although the data set follows a fractal presentation, AIDS percentages across different countries are not that diversified. This tells us that holistically, the prevalence of AIDS from among the nations do not greatly vary from one another or are not so far from one another. The fractal nature of AIDS prevalence signifies that there is an observed fluctuation in the number of people who gets infected with the disease.

FRACTAL SPECTRUM OF AIDS PREVALENCE

The concentration of data is in the medium scale of the fractal spectrum. Meanwhile, at the lower scale, more data with higher values appear to converge. This says otherwise to the data at the bigger scale which practically contains lower percentages of AIDS prevalence. Further, the spectrum shows that the countries with high AIDS prevalence have a higher fractal dimension as compared to the countries with lower AIDS prevalence.

IV. ANALYSIS

On a macro level or worldwide scale, low fractality in AIDS prevalence is observed and majority of the countries are in the mean fractal value. However, on a micro level, high fractality

is observed among the countries with low AIDS prevalence. Barret and Swallow (2003) cites two kinds of poverty: the transitory poverty and persistent poverty. In their paper entitled Fractal Poverty Traps, they suggested multi-scalar approach to the persistent poverty traps. Thus, the result implies that a persistent fractal problem like AIDS needs multi-scale approach. The approach will depend on the fractality dimension of the developed, developing and under- developed countries.

V. CONCLUSION

Countries with high percentage of HIV infections have high fractal dimensions, which means that these countries vary diversely in terms of the number of AIDS infected people. The fluctuations or spikes in the prevalence of AIDS across these countries appear to be wide and very irregular. The vast fractality of AIDS prevalence may be attributed to the diversity in population, cultural practices, technological advancement, literacy levels, political strifes and socio-economic instability in the world. This chaos called HIV which beset the world is highly fractal with low fractal prevalence on a macro level (across economic demographics all over the world) and high fractal prevalence on a micro level (among under-developed) countries.

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